

ATTITUDE OF COTTON GROWERS IN VIDARBHA TOWARDS IMPROVED INTEGRATED MANAGEMENT PRACTICES OF PINK BOLLWORM

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Abstract:

Vidarbha is an important cotton growing region in Maharashtra. In Vidarbha region, cotton is the most important cash crop grown. Cotton yield primarily depends on weather, pest, diseases and management practices. Pink bollworm (PBW) is one of the major damaging insect pests of cotton. Farmer's attitude is one of the important components that plays a vital role in convert or overt behaviour. Present study was conducted on six district namely Buldhana, Akola, Amravati, Yavatmal, Wardha and Nagpur on the basis of considering the maximum area under cotton cultivation. According to the study, it was observed that nearly one half (51.00%) of the cotton growers were under middle age category 36 to 50 years, 49.33 per cent of them were having semi medium (1.51 to 3.00 ha.) area under cotton cultivation. Majority 82.67 per cent of them were done sowing of cotton on set of monsoon, While 54.33 per cent them were following kharif + rabi season cropping pattern. Nearly two fifth i.e. 40.67 per cent of them were having their annual income Rs. 1,50,000 to 300000/- and 48.33 per cent of them were having medium level availability of input infrastructure facilities. Further 52.67 per cent had no membership of informal and formal organization. While 67.00 per cent of them had used medium level of extension contact. Majority 67.67 per cent of the cotton growers had medium economic motivation and 58.00 per cent of them medium risk preference level. More than one half (57.00%) of the cotton growers had the favourable attitude toward management practices of PBW.

Key Words: Attitude, Cotton growers, pink bollworm management practices

Introduction

Pink bollworm pest (PBW) is an important determinant of the prosperity of the cotton growers in Vidarbha. The impact of pink bollworm attack has been felt the most in backward regions of Vidarbha and Marathwada, where cotton is cultivated as the main cash crop across 14 districts. In Vidarbha, 14.16 lakh cotton growing farmers have suffered losses and 14.91 lakh hectares of cotton sown land has been affected due to pink bollworm. Most of the farmers have failed to recover even the cultivation cost from the main cash crop. Pink bollworm attack poses several challenges for the distraught farmers as well as the ruling government, scientists, extension personnel. With this background to accelerate rate of adoption of any technology, positivism of farmers in terms of skill, knowledge and attitude is very much essential. Attitude is one of the important components that plays a vital role in convert or overt behaviour. Attitude towards IPM, knowledge of IPM and risk bearing ability are the important factors influencing adoption of IPM (Mainframe, 2002). Hence, Looking to this fact attitude of cotton growers towards improved integrated management practices of Pink boll worm has been considered in present study with the following objectives.

Sum of attitude score
obtained by a respondent

$$\text{Attitude Index} = \frac{\text{Sum of attitude score obtained by a respondent}}{\text{Sum of obtainable attitude score}} \times 100$$

To study the profile of the cotton growers in Vidarbha

To study the attitude of cotton growers towards management of pink bollworm in Vidarbha

Materials and Methods

For present study on the basis of the maximum area under cotton cultivation six districts in Vidarbha namely Buldana, Akola, Amravati, Yavatmal, Wardha and Nagpur were selected. From this district twelve taluka were purposively selected. From each selected taluka five villages and from each selected villages five cotton growers were selected randomly. The data were collected through personal interview schedule, tabulated and analyzed for interpretation of results.

For accessing the attitude level of respondent total 18 important statements were considered in consultation with extension experts, extension professionals, entomologist and available literature. The responses of the respondents were measured on the five point continuum as strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree and it was scored as 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively for positive statements whereas, reverse score was given to negative statements. The obtained attitude raw score by the individual respondent was converted in to attitude index with help of following formula.

On the basis of obtained attitude index score, the respondents were categorized in low, medium and high categories with the help of equal interval method as follows.

Sl. No.	Attitude toward management of PBW	Index score
1.	Less favourable	Up to 33.33
2.	Favourable	33.34 to 66.67
3.	More favourable	Above 66.67

Results and Discussion

Profile of the cotton growers in Vidarbha

1. Age of the selected cotton growers

The data presented in the Table 1 indicated that nearly one half (51.00%) of the cotton growers were under middle age category. Whereas, 27.33 per cent of cotton growers were young age category and 21.67 per cent were under old age category. It is inferred that nearly one half of cotton growers belongs to middle age (36 to 50 years).

2. The education level

It is evident from Table 1 that little less than one half i.e. (45.33%) of the cotton growers were having education up to secondary school (8th to 10th std.) and 25.33 per cent were educated up to higher secondary

school (11th to 12th std.). While, 16.33 per cent had graduate (Above 12th std.) and 11.67 per cent had middle school level education i.e. upto (5th to 7th std.). Only 01.34 per cent cotton growers were having primary level education (1st to 4th std.) and no one respondents found under illiterate category.

3. Occupation of selected cotton growers

It is observed from Table that majority (68.00%) of the cotton growers were having agriculture (farming) as their main occupation. While 17.67 per cent of the cotton growers were doing dairy, goat rearing, poultry and tractor driver as an allied occupation along with agriculture and 08.33 per cent of the cotton growers were engaged as farm labour for wage earning as a supportive endeavor to farming. Furthermore every

little percent i.e. 04.33 per cent of the cotton growers were doing business like tailoring, kirana shop, cloth shop, hotel, krishisevakendra with farming and meager 01.67 percent of them had farming supported by monthly income from salary.

4. Land holding

The result from Table 1 shows that nearly two fifth (40.33%) of the cotton growers were found to be in semi medium category having land holding between 2.01 to 4.00 hectares, followed by 36.67 per cent cotton growers in medium category possessing land of 4.01 to 10 hectares. Whereas 14.33 per cent of cotton growers were small farmers having 1.01 to 2.00 hectares of land holding. While only 07.00 per cent of cotton growers having large land holding above 10.00 hectares and meager (01.67%) of them having marginal land holding up to 1.00 hectares. Thus, it is observed from the above findings that, maximum number of the cotton growers i.e. 40.33 percent had semi medium (between 2.01 to 4.00 ha) land holders.

5. Area under cotton cultivation

It is observed from Table 1 that, nearly half of the cotton growers (49.33%) were having 1.51 to 3.00 ha. area under cotton cultivation. Whereas equal numbers (18.00%) of the cotton growers were having up to 1.50 ha. and 3.01 to 4.50 ha. land under cotton cultivation. While very few of them i.e. 09.00 per cent and 05.67 per cent were having above 6.00 ha. and 4.51 to 6.00 ha. area under cotton cultivation, respectively. Thus, it is inferred from above finding that, nearly half of cotton growers had up to 1.51 to 3.00 ha area under cotton cultivation.

6. Farming experience in cotton cultivation

From Table 1 it is noticed that nearly two fifth (40.33%) of the cotton growers had farming experience between 11 to 20 years, followed by 24.00 per cent of the cotton growers with farming experience between 21 to 30 years. Nearly equal percentage of the cotton growers 18.67 per cent had above 30 years farming experience and 17.00 per cent of them up to 10 years of farming experience in cotton cultivation.

7. Irrigation facilities

From Table 1 revealed that nearly half i.e. 46.00 per cent of the cotton growers were not having any access as source of irrigation. They solely depended on monsoon rains. Followed by nearly half 44.67 per cent of cotton growers who were having open well / tube well as source of irrigation. While remaining 04.33 per cent cotton growers have canal and 02.67 per cent of them have canal plus well as source of irrigation. Only a very few of them i.e. 01.67 per cent were having river as source of irrigation.

8. Cropping pattern

From the Table 1 it is noticed that more than half i.e. (54.33%) cotton growers were following kharif + rabi season cropping pattern, followed by 31.33 per cent of cotton growers who were following only kharif season cropping pattern and 14.33 percent of them were following kharif + rabi + summer season cropping pattern.

9. Annual income

It is apparent from Table 1 that little more than two fifth of the cotton growers i.e. 40.67 per cent were having their annual income between Rs. 1,50,000 to 3,00,000/-, followed by 38.33 per cent of cotton growers were having their annual income up to 1,50,000/-. Whereas, 14.33 per cent and 04.67 per cent of the cotton growers were having annual income up to Rs. 3,00,001 to 4,50,000/- and Rs. 4,50,001 to 6,00,000/- annual income, respectively. However, meager i.e. 02.00 per cent of them were having annual income above Rs. 6, 00,000/-

10. Input infrastructure facilities

As regards to the distribution according to cotton growers as per input infrastructure facilities is mentioned in Table 1 indicated that nearly half i.e. 48.33 per cent cotton growers were having medium level availability of input infrastructure facilities followed by 43.33 per cent cotton growers were having high level availability of input infrastructure facilities and 08.33 per cent of them had low level availability of input infrastructure facilities for management of PBW.

11. Extension contact

It is observed from Table 1 that, majority i.e. 67.00 percent of the cotton growers had medium level of extension contact, followed by about nearly equal percentage of the Bt. cotton growers 16.33 per cent

and 16.67 per cent had low and high level of extension contact, respectively.

12. Economic motivation

The data in the Table 1 shows that, majority of the cotton growers i.e. 67.67 per cent had medium economic motivation, followed by 40.00 per cent of the cotton growers who had low economic motivation. While 14.66 per cent of them had high economic motivation.

13. Risk preference

The result from Table 1 shows that nearly three fifth i.e. (58.00%) of the cotton growers who adopted improved integrated management practices of pink bollworm exhibited medium risk preference level, followed by 22.00 per cent of the cotton growers had low risk preference level and remaining 20.00 percent of them high risk preference.

Attitude of cotton growers toward improved integrated management practices of pink bollworm

The data depicted in Table 02 revealed that, less than one fourth of cotton growers were strongly agreed with statement that, installation of pheromone traps helps the farmer for getting warning of PBW infestation on crop (24.00%), and it is effective techniques for mass trapping of PBW (21.67%), followed by (19.00%) of the cotton growers strongly agreed with use of trichocard is effective to control PBW at egg stage and (17.33 %) of them also strongly agreed with spray of chemical insecticides should be used only at the economic threshold level (ETL) of PBW, respectively.

From the Table 02 over an half of cotton growers were agreed with statements that, installation of pheromone traps helps the farmer for getting warning of PBW infestation on crop (59.33%), I believe that appropriate and timely management practices can control PBW on cotton (56.00%), I would like to encourage cotton growers for using university recommended integrated management practices to control pink bollworm (51.67%), followed by less than half of the cotton growers were agreed with statements that, timely sowing with early duration varieties of cotton crop can escape the PBW infestation (44.67%), while equal percent of them agree the statements that pheromone trap is effective techniques for mass trapping of PBW and continuous pesticides application increases resistance to PBW (42.67%). Over one third of cotton growers recorded their agreement towards statements that PBW can also check up by crop rotation (39.00%), spray of chemical insecticides should be used only at the economic threshold level (ETL) of PBW (32.67%), respectively. However nearly one third agree the statements that PBW cannot manage through summer deep ploughing in 2-3 years as well as simultaneous removal of stubbles (34.33%).

From the Table 02 observed that the cotton growers were undecided with statements that using improved integrated management against PBW increases profit of cotton growers (42.67%), use of recommended chemicals insecticides as per their recommended doses at economic threshold level (ETL) against PBW do not develop resistance (38.67%), PBW cannot manage through summer deep ploughing in 2-3 years as well as simultaneous removal of stubbles (37.33%), timely sowing with early duration varieties of cotton crop can escape the PBW infestation (29.67%), use of NSKE 5 per cent is not effective against PBW at initial of pest infestation (29.33%) respectively.

However, more than half of the cotton growers disagreed with statements that, use of chemical insecticides as per toxicity label are not essential (green, red, blue and red) (58.67%), I believe that various recommended management practices for PBW are time consuming and so they should not be implemented. (55.33%) by adopting of intercropping like Udid/ Mung/ Jowar / Tur the losses due to PBW cannot be minimized (54.00%) respectively.

Less than half of the cotton growers disagreed with statements that, use of refuge crop for PBW control is not effective practices (48.67%), use of NSKE 5 per cent is not effective against PBW at initial of pest infestation (44.67%). Whereas, nearly one third of the cotton growers disagreed with statements that, identifying and destroying of "rosette-

bloom or rosette –flower” is easy technique and use of trichocard is effective to control PBW at egg stage (32.00%), respectively.

From the Table 02 observed that, more than one fourth of the cotton growers were strongly disagree with statements that, identifying and destroying of “rosette-bloom or rosette –flower” is easy technique (26.67%), followed by little more than one fifth of them, use of chemical insecticides as per toxicity label are not essential (green, red, blue and red) (20.33%), use of refuge crop for PBW control is not effective practices (19.00%) and use of NSKE 5 per cent is not effective against PBW at initial of pest infestation (17.00%) respectively.

From above finding it is inferred that nearly three fifth (59.33%) of cotton growers have agreed with the statement installation of pheromone traps helps the farmer for getting warning of PBW infestation on crop and (42.67%) of them agreed with the another statement of pheromone trap that it is effective techniques for mass trapping of PBW. This might be due pheromone trap are more economically viable than the use of conventional insecticides. While most of the cotton growers (56.00% and 51.67%) have agreed with the statement of I believe that appropriate and timely management practices can control PBW on cotton and I would like to encourage cotton growers for using improved integrated management practices to control pink bollworm, respectively. However, 42.67 per cent cotton growers agree with the statement that continuous pesticides application increases resistance to PBW statement this the possible reason behind that the cotton growers realized that use of repeatedly and overdoses of injudicious chemical insecticides helps to PBW develop resistance against chemical insecticides and 44.67 per cent of them agree with timely sowing with early duration varieties of cotton crop can escape the PBW infestation statement this might be due that majority of cotton growers cultivated cotton crop in rainfed condition and the time of sowing in rained cotton is on onset of monsoon.

With regards to disagreement of statement it is inferred that maximum number i.e. (58.67%) of cotton growers disagree with the statement “Use of chemical insecticides as per toxicity label are not essential (green, red, blue and red)”. The possible reason might be that over a half of cotton growers have knowledge about all chemical insecticides have some level of toxicity. Whereas, 55.33 per cent of cotton growers disagree with the statement “I believe that various recommended management practices for PBW are time consuming and so they should not be implemented”. The possible reason could be acceptance of university recommended management practices to control pink bollworm by cotton growers. While with the statement of “Use of refuge crop for PBW control is not effective practices” 48.67 per cent cotton growers responses to disagreed with this statement. This might be due to fact that most of the cotton growers have knowledge about the strategy of growing 'refuge' plants around the Bt cotton plants that PBW exclusively feed on cotton to prevent or delay the development of Bt-resistant insects and save from PBW. Furthermore (44.67 %) of them disagree with the statement “use of NSKE 5 per cent is not effective against PBW at initial of pest infestation” This might be due that cotton growers observed NSKE played a major role against PBW.

Attitude level of cotton growers towards improved integrated management practices of pink bollworm

The data presented in Table 03 regarding attitude level of cotton growers toward management of pink bollworm revealed that, nearly to three fifth (57.00%) of the cotton growers were belonged to the favourable attitude category, followed by (39.33%) of them were having more favourable attitude toward management practices of PBW and least (03.67%) of the them were belonged to less favourable attitude category.

Thus, it could be concluded that nearly to three fifth (57.00%) of the cotton growers were belonged to the favourable attitude towards improved integrated management practices of PBW. This might be due to their exposure with scientific literature, field day and constant touch with extension personals. In addition to this most of cotton growers are educated which helps to acquire unquestionably technical knowledge and also these management practices. According to Ajzen and Fishbein (2005), the theory of planned behaviour is built on the assumption that an individual's behaviours are derived from his or her intention, which is primarily determined by attitude. This is also supported by the study, which finds that cotton growers with a positive attitude toward improved management practices of pink bollworm are more likely to adopt improved management practices. This implies that in terms of policy making, to build up cotton growers positive attitude toward management practices of pink bollworm.

These findings corroborate with the findings reported by Shinde (2011), Kadam (2016), Rathwa (2018) and Dipika Aglawe (2019).

Conclusion

The findings revealed that nearly one half (51.00%) of the cotton growers were under middle age category 36 to 50 years, little less than one half 45.33 per cent of them were educated up to secondary school and 68.00 per cent were having agriculture as their main occupation. Nearly two fifth i.e. 40.33 per cent of cotton growers had semi medium (2.01 to 4.00 ha) land holders and farming experience of 11 to 20 years. Nearly half 49.33 per cent of them were having semi medium (1.51 to 3.00 ha.) area under cotton cultivation and 46.00 per cent of the cotton growers were not having any source for irrigation. Majority 82.67 per cent of them were done sowing of cotton on set of monsoon. Further 54.33 per cent cotton growers were following kharif + rabi season cropping pattern and 40.67 per cent of them were having their annual income Rs. 1,50,000 to 300000/-. Nearly half 48.33 per cent of them were having medium level availability of input infrastructure facilities and 52.67 per cent had no membership of informal and formal organization. While 67.00 per cent of them had used medium level of extension contact. Majority 67.67 per cent of the cotton growers had medium economic motivation and 58.00 per cent of them medium risk preference level. More than one half (57.00%) of the cotton growers had the favourable attitude toward management practices of PBW.

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Table 1: Distribution of the cotton growers according to their profile characteristics

Sl. No	Particulars	Respondents (n=300)	
		Frequency	Percentage
1.	Age of the cotton growers		
	Young (UP to 35)	82	27.33
	Middle (36 to 50)	153	51.00
	Old (Above 50)	65	21.67
	Total	300	100.00
2.	Education (Std.)		
	Illiterate (No Schooling)	00	00.00
	Primary School (1 st to 4 th std)	04	01.34
	Middle School (5 th to 7 th Std)	35	11.67
	Secondary School (8 th to 10 th Std)	136	45.33
	Higher Secondary School (11 th to 12 th Std)	79	25.33
	Graduate (Above 12 th Std)	49	16.33
	Total	300	100.00
3.	Occupation		
	Agriculture Farming	204	68.00
	Agriculture + Labour	25	08.33
	Agriculture + allied Occupation	53	17.67
	Agriculture + business	13	04.33
	Agriculture + Service	05	01.67
	Total	300	100.00
4.	Land holding (ha.)		
	Marginal (Up to 1.00 ha)	05	01.67
	Small (1.01 to 2.00 ha)	43	14.33
	Semi – Medium (2.01 to 4.00)	121	40.33
	Medium (4.01 to 10.00 ha)	110	36.67
	Large (Above 10.00)	21	07.00
	Total	300	100.00
5	Area Under cotton cultivation (ha.)		
	Up to 1.50 ha.	54	18.00
	1.51 to 3.00 ha.	148	49.33
	3.01 to 4.50 ha.	54	18.00
	4.51 to 6.00 ha.	17	05.67
	Above 6.00 ha.	27	09.00
	Total	300	100.00
6.	Farming experience in year		
	Up to 10 years	51	17.00
	11 to 20 years	121	40.33
	21 to 30 years	72	24.00
	Above 30 years	56	18.67
	Total	300	100.00
7.	Source of irrigation		
	No source/rainfed	142	47.33
	River	05	01.67
	Well/Tube well	132	44.00
	Canal	13	04.33
	Canal + Well	08	02.67
	Total	300	100.00
8	Cropping pattern		
	Kharif	94	31.33
	Kharif + Rabi	163	54.33
	Kharif + Rabi + Summer	43	14.34
	Total	300	100.00
9.	Annual Income (Rs.)		
	Up to Rs. 1,50,000 /-	115	38.33
	Rs. 1,50,001 to 3,00,000 /-	122	40.67
	Rs. 3,00,001 to 4,50,000 /-	43	14.33
	Rs. 4,50,001 to 6,00,000 /-	14	04.67
	Above Rs. 6,00,000 /-	06	02.00
	Total	300	100.00
10.	Input Infrastructure facilities		

	Low	25	08.34
	Medium	145	48.33
	High	130	43.33
	Total	300	100.00
11.	Extension Contact		
	Low	49	16.33
	Medium	201	67.00
	High	50	16.67
	Total	300	100.00
12.	Economic motivation		
	Low	53	17.67
	Medium	203	67.67
	High	44	14.66
	Total	300	100.00
13.	Risk preference		
	Low	66	22.00
	Medium	174	58.00
	High	60	20.00
	Total	300	100.00

Table 2. Distribution of the cotton growers according to their attitude towards improved integrated management practices of pink bollworm

Sl. No.	Attitude towards improved integrated management practices of pink bollworm	SA	A	UD	DA	SDA
1.	Using improved integrated management practices against PBW increases profit of cotton growers.	48 (16.00)	93 (31.00)	128 (42.67)	29 (09.67)	02 (0.66)
2.	PBW cannot manage through summer deep ploughing in 2-3 years as well as simultaneous removal of stubbles.	55 (18.33)	103 (34.33)	112 (37.33)	29 (09.67)	01 (0.34)
3.	PBW can also check up by crop rotation.	22 (07.33)	117 (39.00)	86 (28.67)	62 (20.67)	13 (04.33)
4.	By adopting of intercropping like Udid/Mung/Jowar / Tur the losses due to PBW cannot be minimized.	17 (05.67)	73 (24.33)	32 (10.67)	162 (54.00)	16 (05.33)
5.	Spray of chemical insecticides should be used only at the economic threshold level (ETL) of PBW.	52 (17.33)	98 (32.67)	68 (22.67)	73 (24.33)	09 (03.00)
6.	Pheromone trap is effective techniques for mass trapping of PBW.	65 (21.67)	128 (42.67)	86 (28.66)	12 (04.00)	09 (03.00)
7.	Continuous pesticides application increases resistance to PBW.	43 (14.33)	128 (42.67)	71 (23.67)	47 (15.67)	11 (03.66)
8.	Timely sowing with early duration varieties of cotton crop can escape the PBW infestation.	51 (17.00)	134 (44.67)	89 (29.67)	16 (05.33)	10 (03.33)
9.	I believe that appropriate and timely management practices can control PBW on cotton.	47 (15.67)	168 (56.00)	56 (18.67)	29 (09.66)	0.00 (0.00)
10.	Use of refuge crop for PBW control is not effective practices.	09 (03.00)	49 (16.33)	39 (13.00)	146 (48.67)	57 (19.00)
11.	Identifying and destroying of "rosette-bloom or rosette -flower" is easy technique.	08 (02.67)	91 (30.33)	25 (08.33)	96 (32.00)	80 (26.67)
12.	Use of trichocard is effective to control PBW at egg stage.	57 (19.00)	84 (28.00)	36 (12.00)	96 (32.00)	27 (09.00)
13.	Use of recommended chemicals insecticides as per their recommended doses at economic threshold level (ETL) against PBW do not develop resistance.	35 (11.67)	104 (34.67)	116 (38.67)	34 (11.33)	11 (03.66)
14.	I believe that various recommended management practices for PBW are time consuming and so they should not be implemented.	01 (0.34)	33 (11.00)	67 (22.33)	166 (55.33)	33 (11.00)
15.	I would like to encourage cotton growers for using University recommended integrated management practices to control pink bollworm.	36 (12.00)	155 (51.67)	84 (28.00)	24 (08.00)	01 (0.33)
16.	Installation of pheromone traps helps the farmer for getting warning of PBW infestation on crop.	72 (24.00)	178 (59.33)	37 (12.33)	11 (03.67)	02 (0.67)
17.	Use of chemical insecticides as per toxicity label are not essential (green,red,blue and red) .	02 (00.67)	30 (10.00)	31 (10.33)	176 (58.67)	61 (20.33)

18.	Use of NSKE 5% is not effective against PBW at initial of pest infestation.	10 (03.33)	17 (05.67)	88 (29.33)	134 (44.67)	51 (17.00)
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Figures in parentheses indicate percentage

Table 3. Distribution of the cotton growers according to their attitude level towards improved integrated management practices of pink bollworm

Sl. No.	Attitude level	Respondents (n=300)	
		Frequency	Percentage
1.	Less favourable (Up to 33.33)	11	03.67
2.	Favourable (33.34 to 66.67)	171	57.00
3.	More favourable (Above 66.67)	118	39.33
	Total	300	100.00